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ЖУРНАЛ ГЕПАТО-ГАСТРОЭНТЕРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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A CASE OF LONG-TERM OBSERVATION OF A CHILD WITH SANFILIPPO SYNDROME

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ANNOTATION

Mucopolysaccharidosis type III (Sanfilippo syndrome) is a rare multisystem disease caused by the accumulation of glycosaminoglycans (GAG) in cells of various organs, leading to impaired function, specific phenotypic signs and progressive neurocognitive disorders. Polymorphism and non-specificity of clinical manifestations are a common cause of late diagnosis of MPS.

We present our own prolonged clinical observation of a type III MPS case in a patient who was under our supervision for 12 years. The diagnosis was established and confirmed at the age of three. The disease manifested itself by neuropsychiatric regression and systemic somatic manifestations. Motor deficits, cognitive impairments with the development of dementia and recurrent aspiration syndrome progressed in the dynamics of the child.

Keywords: Sanfilippo syndrome, mucopolysaccharidosis, children, neurocognitive disorders

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СЛУЧАЙ ДЛИТЕЛЬНОГО НАБЛЮДЕНИЯ ЗА РЕБЕНКОМ С СИНДРОМОМ САНФИЛИППО

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мукополисахаридоз III типа (синдром Санфилиппо) является редким мультисистемным заболеванием, обусловленным накоплением гликозаминогликанов (ГАГ) в клетках различных органов, приводящее к нарушению их функции, специфическим фенотипическим признакам и прогрессирующим нейрокогнитивным нарушениям. Полиморфизм и неспецифичность клинических проявлений являются частой причиной поздней диагностики МПС.

Представлено собственное пролонгированное клиническое наблюдение случая МПС III типа у пациента, находившегося под нашим наблюдением в течение 12 лет. Диагноз установлен и подтвержден в возрасте трех лет. Заболевание манифестировало психоневрологическим регрессом и системными соматическими проявлениями. В динамике у ребенка прогрессировали моторный дефицит, когнитивные нарушения с развитием деменции и рецидивирующий аспирационный синдром.

Ключевые слова: синдром Санфилиппо, мукополисахаридоз, дети, нейрокогнитивные нарушения.

Sanfilippo syndrome or mucopolysaccharidosis type III (MPS III) is a lysosomal accumulation disease with an autosomal recessive type of inheritance caused by mutations in the genes encoding the synthesis of enzymes involved in the cleavage of heparan sulfate, leading to its accumulation in lysosomes and manifested clinically, first of all, progressive dementia, as well as various somatic disorders [1]. Type III MPS is probably the most common form of all mucopolysaccharidoses. The cause of the development of the disease is numerous mutations in the genes of SGSH (17q25.3), NAGLU(17q21.2), HGSNAT(8p11.21) and GNS (12q14), responsible for the production of four different enzymes and corresponding to four subtypes of this MPS - MPS IIIA, B, C and D [2].

The total frequency of all four subtypes ranges from 0.17 to 2.35 per 100,000 live births, with the frequency of the most common MPS IIIA up to 1.62 per 100,000 [3]. According to other data, the incidence of the disease is 0.28-4.1 per 100,000 live births [4, 5]. The total number of such patients in the world is 12-19 thousand [6]. The prevalence of type III MPS in the Russian Federation according to N.V. Buchinskaya (2015) ranges from 0.88 in the Northwestern to 0.37 per 100,000 in the Central Federal Districts.

The clinical picture of the disease is dominated by neuropathic manifestations, both in terms of time of manifestation and severity. Distinct behavioral disorders in the form of disinhibition, aggressiveness, inadequate emotional reactions, sleep disorders, inability to learn and communicate are formed by the age of 3-4. Subsequently, there is a regression of motor skills, bulbar disorders, convulsions.

The lesion of the musculoskeletal system is variable and may include mild or moderate articular contractures, vertebral deformities, hip dysplasia, premature growth arrest, as well as specific changes in the articulation of 1-2 cervical vertebrae (which may pose problems during surgical and anesthetic interventions). The most demonstrative somatic problems of children with type III MPS include hyperplasia of the lymphoid tissue of the pharynx with the development of recurrent infections of the ENT organs, chronic otitis and hearing loss (both with conductive and sensorineural components), obstructive sleep apnea. The combination of bulbar and obstructive respiratory disorders contributes to the development of aspiration syndrome, repeated pneumonia and bronchoobstructive syndrome are characteristic. Hepatomegaly (less often hepatosplenomegaly) is also less pronounced and occurs in not many more than half of patients. Gastroenterological manifestations of the disease in the form of diarrhea and constipation are observed in most patients. Cardiopathy with valvular disorders and myocardial hypertrophy rarely reaches manifest severity [7-9].

Subtypes of type III MPS clinically manifest themselves differently. Subtypes A and B are similar in clinic and are characterized by the most aggressive course with rapid development of dementia and motor disorders and a life expectancy of 15-19 years. Subtypes C and D are much rarer and have greater variability, later manifestation and a "soft" course. There may be "atypical" cases with non-rough partial behavioral and speech disorders. It is subtypes C and D, as well as some complex heterozygotes of subtypes A and B, that most often have late diagnosis or remain undiagnosed [10,11]. There is currently no effective treatment of type III MPS, the basis of patient management is symptomatic therapy, including with the use of neuroleptics and anticonvulsants, as well as socio-pedagogical support.

CASE REPORT

For the first time, the child was admitted to a children's clinical hospital at the age of 3 with stings for subfebrile temperature, difficulty

nasal breathing (night "snoring"), a highly productive paroxysmal cough, shortness of breath. At the place of residence, he received antibacterial therapy without effect.

From the anamnesis: was born from the III normal pregnancy, the II birth at 35-36 weeks, premature discharge of amniotic fluid, anhydrous period of 14 hours, the weakness of labor, cesarean section. At birth, the weight is 2750 g, the body length is 50 cm, the Apgar score is 6/7 points. After birth, he was in the pathology department of newborns with a diagnosis of Perinatal CNS lesion, motor disorders syndrome. Congenital pneumonia. Neonatal jaundice. Breastfeeding up to 6 months. At 12 months, with a height of 76 cm, he weighed 10200 g. He held his head from 2 months, sat down on his own - from 8 months, walked without support from 14 months. By the age of 1.5 years, speech was represented by several syllabic words. Vaccinations are made by age. Heredity is not burdened: parents and sister are healthy, they do not have any phenotypic features. The child lives in a remote rural area, the social and hygienic conditions and care are satisfactory.

Since the age of two, there has been a regression of psychomotor skills: inversion of sleep with wakefulness at night, decreased interest in playing together and emotional coloring of communication, easily irritated, lameness appeared when walking. From the same age, recurrent respiratory episodes were diagnosed, expressed by a violation of nasal breathing, snuffling. In the third year of life, attacks of psychomotor agitation appeared, accompanied by prolonged screaming with a grimace, sharp movements, resistance when trying to calm the child. I didn't react enough to the addressed speech. Night sleep disturbances increased, night snoring with episodes of apnea was observed. Hyperactivity was absent, parents had problems controlling the child's behavior, began choking on liquid food when feeding. Dysuric phenomena appeared in the form of increased urination, anxiety, frequent loss of urine, there was no control of defecation.

At the age of 3, he was hospitalized for the first time for acute respiratory infection. Upon admission, physical development is above average +1.9SD, harmonious, height 103 cm, weight 20 kg. During the examination, phenotypic signs drew attention to themselves: rough facial features, wide bridge of the nose, short neck, epicanthus, thickened tip of the nose, stiff dry hair, dark fused eyebrows (Fig. 1)

There was a moderately pronounced deformation of the hands according to the type of "clawed paw" with shortening of the fingers. Nasal breathing is difficult, hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils of the 2nd degree, loose, edematous, without plaque. The skin feels dense (thickened). There was shortness of breath with a breathing rate of up to 40 in 1 minute and auxiliary movements in the shoulder girdle. Moist, small-bubbly wheezes were heard in the lungs on both sides. The abdomen was moderately enlarged in volume, an increase in the liver and spleen was determined to 6 and 4 cm, respectively, with moderate compaction. Umbilical hernia, deformity of the hands according to the type of "claws-stop paws". Episodes of liquid stool were noted.

Upon examination, the child is easily excitable, motor disinhibition. He was sitting on his own, walking unsteadily with support by the hand, he could fall without support. Speech is represented by several syllabic words, a low voice, and also made various unintelligible sounds. Echocardiography of the heart revealed an overload of the right departments. The phenotypic features of the patient and the dynamics of the neuropsychiatric status made it possible to suspect mucopolysaccharidosis. The diagnosis was confirmed in the laboratory of the Federal State Medical University "MGNC" by a biochemical method for increased urinary excretion of heparan sulfate (107.9

mg/mmol creatinine) and deficiency of heparan-N-sulfatase activity.

Subsequently, the child was hospitalized twice in the Department of Neuropsychiatry and Psychosomatic Pathology of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "NMIC of Children's Health" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation with the diagnosis: Mucopolysaccharidosis type III A (Sanfilippo syndrome); delayed speech development, pseudobulbar syndrome, secondary cardiomyopathy (heart failure), mitral, tricuspid, aortic valves and pulmonary artery valve, NC 1 art.), multiple contractures of large and small joints of the extremities, stenosis of the cervical spine. Therapy included periciazine (neuleptil) and resperidone.

During the observation period, there was a slow progression of symptoms to a complete regression of speech, self-service skills and self-control. The greatest problems in the care of the child were nighttime sleep disorders and bouts of psychomotor agitation with autoaggression in the daytime. Gradually, problems with eating disappeared: frequent choking, coughing during feeding, and liquid food entering the nose were observed. During a night's sleep, multiple episodes of obstructive apnea were noted. Did not control pelvic functions. Acute respiratory infections and aspiration episodes 3-5 times a year led to the development of bronchial obstruction with respiratory failure. Otitis was repeatedly diagnosed.

By the age of 12, the child had a height of 148 cm, weight 38 kg. He was incapable of self-service, helpless, moved with support or in a wheelchair. Inappropriate behavior was noted, he made purposeless and spontaneous movements, including self-traumatic ones. When trying to inspect the excitement increased. I recognized my loved ones and carried out their simple commands, briefly focused my attention when communicating with my parents. Speech in the form of unmodulated, negatively colored sounds. He did not control the functions of the pelvic organs. There was a significant violation of nasal breathing, a large

tongue, gum hyperplasia. The function of swallowing is moderately impaired, choked with food and liquid. The abdomen is protruding, the edge of the liver was palpated 2 cm below the costal arch, elastic, the spleen is the edge in the hypochondrium. A small umbilical hernia, moderately pronounced multiple contractures of both large and small joints, asymmetry of posture. Stool 1 time in 2-3 days, with a tendency to constipation (Fig. 2).

At the age of 13, the child suffered severe polysegmental pneumonia with pleurisy and respiratory insufficiency of the 2nd degree. Increased dysphagia, inability to consume a sufficient amount of food, loss of body weight and violation of nutritional status were the grounds for gastrostomy.

At the outpatient stage of palliative treatment, he received periciazine. During the stay at home, episodes of desaturation after meals and during sleep were observed up to 88-90%, which required additional subsidies of moistened oxygen, for which the child was provided with an oxygen concentrator. Progressive neurological disorders were noted in the dynamics of the condition, manifested by spasticity and a single episode of clonic-tonic seizures, which required modification of therapy with the appointment of gabapentin and baclofen.

CONCLUSION

The presented patient has a classic clinical picture of type III MPS with aggressive development of cognitive and motor disorders at 2-3 years of life, characteristic phenotypic and somatic manifestations of the disease. This case demonstrates the multiplicity of problems and the need for interaction between doctors of various specialties. We would like to note the complexity of pharmacological correction of psychoneurological symptoms and the high risk of side effects of drugs and their interaction.

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